

TOWARDS BULK NANOBUBBLE GENERATION: DEVELOPMENT OF A BULK NANOBUBBLE GENERATOR BASED ON HYDRODYNAMIC CAVITATION

Omar El Arwadi, Abu Samah Zuruzi

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Alfaisal University,
Riyadh, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

ABSTRACT

Nanobubbles are gaining much interest due to potential applications ranging from waste water treatment to drug delivery. This paper describes development of a prototype device to generate bulk nanobubbles in water. The device works by inducing hydrodynamic cavitation in which macro bubbles formed implode into bulk nanobubbles by local pressure changes in the device. As the water circulates in the device, the local pressure drop below the saturated vapour pressure of the liquid causing cavitation. Preliminary ambient testing of the prototype was carried out. The prototype was fabricated using a photopolymer by 3-D printing.

KEYWORDS

Nanobubble, Bulk Nanobubble, Nanobubble generator, 3-D printing, additive manufacturing.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bubbles are gas-filled structures enclosed by a thin skin or boundary. In liquids such as water, the boundary comprise of a layer of gas molecules adsorbed on the liquid surface with surface tension γ . The type of gas and skin of a bubble and the type of liquid the bubble is in obviously determine the behaviour of the bubble [1]. Nanobubbles are defined as bubbles in the range between 10 nm to 1 μm in diameter [2]. Nanobubbles found on surfaces are necessarily spherical domes and often termed as surface nanobubbles. While surface nanobubbles have been visually using atomic force microscopy Nanobubbles can also while those existing in liquid are often known as bulk nanobubbles.

The theoretical explanation for the existence of nanobubbles are somewhat unclear. The Laplace pressure ΔP inside a bubble of radius R with surface tension γ is given by:

$$\Delta P = \frac{4\gamma}{R}$$

According to this traditional understanding, nanobubbles, by virtue of their small radius of curvature, will have high Laplace pressure. This large pressure should result in gas diffusion across the boundary and consequently these nanobubbles will dissolve and hence are unstable [3]. However, a growing body of experimental data supporting the existence of surface nanobubbles have recently been published. Surface nanobubbles have been observed using atomic force

microscopy [1, 4] and optical system equipped with a polarized laser as well as fluorescence microscopy [5, 6]. Much less evidence is available to show the existence of bulk nanobubbles. However, oxygen bulk nanobubbles have been reported in recent studies using transmission electron microscope (TEM) with the freeze-fractured replica method [7]. Similarly, cryo-TEM has been used to visualize lipid and polymer-stabilized perfluoro carbon bulk nanobubbles which is an important step in mediated drug delivery [8].

A few techniques have been used to form nanobubbles. Mechanical swirling of water using a hand mixer had been reported to form nanobubbles less than 100 nm which are stable in water containing 1 % ethanol up to a month [9]. Size and occurrence of nanobubbles were reported to be modulated by presence of NaCl. Electrolysis of distilled water using copper electrodes were able to generate nanobubbles at a rate proportional to the applied voltage [10]. Plants germinated with nanobubbled water were reported to have favourable properties such as enhanced growth rate which are attributed to enhanced nutrient absorption.

This paper describes the design and development of a prototype bulk nanobubble generator. The prototype generates bulk nanobubbles based on hydrodynamic cavitation. The theoretical basis, first-generation design of the prototype and testing method are described herein. The manuscript describes attempting to form bulk nanobubbles using a 3D printed device.

2. DESIGN AND FABRICATION

2.1. Fabrication Process

The prototype device was fabricated by 3-D printing using stereo lithography (SLA) technology. A Formlabs 3-D printer (model Form 2) equipped with 405nm laser was used to fabricate the prototype device. Layer thickness was set 100 μm and laser spot size at full width half-maximum (FWHM) was nominally 140 μm . The device can be scaled dimensionally depending on applications. In this paper, the prototype device fabricated has a diameter of 9 cm and took about 20 hrs to build. To facilitate formation of bubbles, a hydrophobic photopolymer resin was used for all components of the nanobubble generator device [11].

2.2. Design of Nanobubble Generator prototype

Figure 1. Bulk nanobubble generator prototype: (a) exploded view and (b) side view with dimensions in mm.

The bulk nanobubble generator comprise of three parts. **Figure 1** shows an exploded schematic view of the device. The top lid contains a feedthrough hole for water inlet and secures the core to the casing. Water flows through a nozzle and built-in channels in the core which increases its velocity. As water flows and velocity increases, cavitation occurs in the water when the local static pressure drops below the vapour pressure of water which is 2.3 kPa at 293 K [12]. Water with forming (or formed) cavitation exits at apertures with 1.57 mm diameter; inset in **Figure 1**.

Water then flows into channels between the core and casing as shown in **Figure 2** at a specific flow velocity determined from geometry of nozzle and channels in the core. The combination of pressure and kinetic energy in this stage creates further hydrodynamic cavitation downstream at local constrictions generating higher energy cavitation bubbles. Finally, water reaches the outlet which has features to cause subsequent growth and collapse of the cavitation bubbles.

Figure 2. Water flows channels between the core and casing with local constrictions

3. TESTING OF PROTOTYPE

As discussed in the introduction section, formation of bulk nanobubbles needs elaborate characterization tools such as electron microscopy to prove. However, in this paper, we tested the ability of the core of the prototype to generate macroscale bubbles from water stream in laminar flow.

Figure 3 shows time lapse images of the core of the prototype with water flowing in through a transparent tube at water inlet point. Water starts flowing into the prototype at 0 s. A 4 s interval was observed between the time water flows into the prototype as formation of bubbles at the aperture. This interval corresponds to time needed to fill the cavities and channels in the prototype. Microscale and macroscale bubbles were formed 4 s after the flow of water into the device. It was observed that microscale bubbles coalesce to form larger macroscale bubbles. Similarly, it is postulated that microscale bubbles observed were formed from coalescences of nanoscale bubbles. After 8 s, more bubbles were observed with newer and smaller bubbles being generated.

Testing of the prototype was done in air to facilitate observation of bubbles, Figure 3. In actual operation, the prototype will be immersed in water or liquid. Under such conditions, it can be

expected that the size of bubbles will be smaller due pressure from surrounding liquid. Also, the prototype has been shown to be able to continuously generate microbubbles.

Figure 3. Time lapsed images showing bubble formed at a single aperture hole

There are obvious limitations of the present study. As discussed in the introduction section, the nanobubble characterization needs tools such as electron microscopy to prove the device generates nanoscale bubbles. Our future will focus on studies that combines the nanobubble generator with instrumentation that enables detection of nanobubbles. Furthermore, improvements to the first-generation prototype will be made to increase its efficiency and flexibility for deployment for a wide range of applications.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, a prototype bulk nanobubble generator device has been fabricated using 3-D printing. This paper described the development of the prototype device and testing the core of the prototype. The prototype successfully generated microscale bubbles using hydrodynamic cavitation. While the formation of bulk nanobubbles was not able to be shown directly, the microscale bubbles were observed which were postulated to result from coalescence of bulk nanobubbles generated by the device.

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AUTHORS

Omar El Arwadi is in his senior year of his Bachelors in Mechanical Engineering program at Alfaisal University. His research interests are in fluids as well as aerospace and aeronautical engineering.

Zuruzi Abu Samah is a professor of mechanical engineering at Alfaisal University. He has served as chair of the department since September 2019. His research interests are in materials and their applications as well as engineering education. He earned his doctoral degree in materials at the University of California, Santa Barbara in 2005.

